

1 **Cover sheet**

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Study title Carryover effects in melatonin suppression
Internal code
Date of protocol (yyyy-MM-dd) 2025-04-28
Version of protocol v1.0.0

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6 **Signatures**

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8 München, 2025-06-24

9 Location, date

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12 Synopsis

13

14 Basic information

Study title Carryover effects in melatonin suppression

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16 Research question

17 Light plays a critical role in regulating human circadian rhythms, influencing the secretion of melatonin
18 and cortisol. The retina, beyond its function in vision, serves as a key input for neuroendocrine
19 regulation. The suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN) acts as the central pacemaker, synchronizing
20 physiological processes in response to environmental light cues. Exposure to artificial light,
21 particularly during evening hours, can significantly alter melatonin suppression, shift circadian
22 rhythms, and impact physiological functions such as core body temperature and glucose metabolism.
23 Recent research highlights that the effects of light on circadian hormones depend on both intensity
24 and spectral composition. Studies indicate that light exposure affects melatonin secretion, but real-
25 world applicability remains limited due to short study durations and disruptions caused by controlled
26 lab environments. An open question is whether preceding light exposure on the day before impacts
27 melatonin suppression. To answer this research question, we will examine carryover effects of light
28 exposure on melatonin suppression by light using a nine-evening in-laboratory pilotstudy.

29 Study design and protocol

30 Healthy participants aged 18 to 40 years will be recruited via flyers and digital advertisements for a
31 nine-day in-laboratory pilotstudy. After giving informed consent for screening, participants will receive
32 an online link to complete a questionnaire about their health status to determine eligibility. If they are
33 eligible to participate in the study, they will be invited to the laboratory. If agreeing to proceed, they
34 will give informed consent for the full pilotstudy. Throughout the pilotstudy, they will wear a wrist-worn
35 activity tracking watch, a continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) device on their arm and a lanyard-
36 worn light exposure logger for the entire starting seven days prior to the first evening in the laboratory.
37 In addition, they will complete a daily sleep diary. A pregnancy test for female participants will be
38 performed once at the first visit, in addition to a drug and alcohol test.

39 On each study evening, participants will be asked to arrive 6.5 hours before their habitual
40 bedtime(HBT), and spend a total of 6 hours in the laboratory, before they leave 30 minutes before
41 their HBT. Upon arrival in the laboratory, they will be provided with a standardised meal (Huel) with a
42 well-balanced macronutrient profile. Then, they will spend 2.5 hours in dim conditions (10 lx). From
43 2.5 hours before HBT to 0.5 before HBT, they will be exposed to one of two stimuli: a dim condition
44 (10 lx), or a bright condition (1000 lx). The final 0.5 hours before HBT will be spent in dim light (10 lx)
45 again, before they leave the laboratory. Every 30 minutes, participants will give a saliva sample for
46 later melatonin analysis as well as sleepiness rating, and every hour, participants will be performing
47 a psychomotor vigilance test. Additionally, skin temperature will be measured using iButtons attached
48 to the neck and ankle. Core body temperature will be monitored using the eCelsius ingestible capsule
49 system. Participants will continue to wear the wrist-worn activity tracking watch, a continuous glucose
50 monitoring (CGM) device on their arm and a lanyard-worn light exposure logger for a week after
51 completion of the final evening.

52 Study sample

53 Inclusion criteria

Domain	Criterion	Assessment method
Age	≥18, ≤40 years of age	Self-report
Biological sex	Men Women with a natural menstrual cycle Women taking monophasic combined oral contraceptives	Self-report
Physical health	Good physical health	Self-report
Mental health	Good mental health	Self-report
Ocular health	Good ocular health	Self-report
Normal colour vision	Normal colour vision	Ishihara-test
Basic English language skills	Ability to comprehend and communicate in basic English	Self-report

54 Exclusion criteria

Domain	Criterion	Assessment method
Biological sex	Women taking any other type of hormonal contraception	Self-report
BMI	<18 or >30	Measured height and weight
Medication use	Any use of medications	Self-report
Smoking	Habitual smoking	Self-report
Epilepsy	Diagnosis of epilepsy	Self-report
Substance abuse	Excessive alcohol use	AUDIT
Sleep	Poor sleep quality	PSQI >5
Chronotype	Extreme chronotype	MCTQ
Shift work	No shift work in the past 3 months	Self-report
Time zone travel	No inter-time zone travel in the past 3 months	Self-report
Pregnancy	Currently pregnant and < 12 months postpartum	Self-report
Endocrinal alternation	No hormonal imbalances	Self-report
Drug use	Any drug detected	AMP, BZD, COC, MOR/OPI, THC panel (nal von minden GmbH)
Alcohol	Any alcohol in breath	Breathalyzer

55

56 Sample size

57 Due to the exploratory character of this pilot study and resource limitations, we will recruit a total of
58 16 participants.

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128 **List of abbreviations**

129

AMP	Amphetamines
AUDIT	Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test
BIA	Bioelectrical impedance analysis
CGM	Continuous Glucose Monitoring
ipRGCs	intrinsically photosensitive retinal ganglion cells
HBT	habitual bedtime
KSS	Karolinska Sleepiness Scale
LEBA	Light Exposure Behaviour Assessment
LED	Light-emitting diode
MCTQ	Munich Chronotype Questionnaire
MHQ	Menstrual History Questionnaire
MOR/OPI	Morphine/Opiates
NSAID	Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug
PI	Principle Investigator
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
PSQI	Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index
M cones	Medium-wavelength-sensitive cones
SCN	Suprachiasmatic nucleus
PLR	Pupillary light reflex
PVT	Psychomotor vigilance test
RHT	Retinohypothalamic tract
THC	Tetrahydrocannabinol

130

131 Background

132 State of the art

133 Ocular light exposure affects human physiology and behaviour (6). Exposure to light in the evening
134 and at night suppresses the production of the endogenous hormone melatonin in a dose-dependent
135 manner, delays the circadian clock and impacts sleep latency and possibly quality. The 'non-visual'
136 effects of light are mediated by a class of retinal ganglion cells that are intrinsically photosensitive
137 through the photopigment melanopsin, known as intrinsically photosensitive retinal ganglion cells
138 (ipRGCs). Melanopsin is sensitive to short-wavelength light (peak wavelength sensitivity near 490 nm
139 in the living human eye after pre-receptor filtering by the lens and ocular media). The ipRGCs project
140 to the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN) in the hypothalamus via the retinohypothalamic tract (RHT),
141 and via a series of synapses that are then linked to the pineal gland and are responsible for melatonin
142 suppression. Melatonin suppression can be calculated based on light exposure duration, lux intensity
143 using an algorithm (7). Short-wavelength light is associated with alertness, thermoregulation, and
144 heart rate (8).

145 There are marked individual differences in the impact of light on melatonin suppression, with some
146 individuals being 60x more sensitive than others (9). The reasons underlying this wide individual
147 variability is unclear and cannot be attributed to prior light exposure, which previously has been
148 identified as a modulator for evening sensitivity to light. The day-to-day variability of melatonin
149 production has thus far not been characterised, nor the impact of the modification of light exposure
150 and melatonin suppression on the days before.

151

152 Summary of proposed study

153 This pilot study aims to investigate the effects of controlled light exposure on physiological and
154 behavioural outcomes in healthy adults aged 18 to 40 years. Participants will be recruited through
155 flyers and digital advertisements and screened using an online health questionnaire to determine
156 eligibility. Those eligible will provide informed consent and undergo additional screening, including a
157 pregnancy test (if applicable) and drug and alcohol testing.

158 Participants will undergo a 23-day protocol (7 days pre-laboratory, 9 laboratory days, 7 days post-
159 laboratory). For seven days before their first laboratory session, participants will wear a wrist-worn
160 activity tracker (ActiGraph), a continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) device, and a lanyard-worn light
161 exposure logger (ActLumus), while also completing a daily sleep diary to monitor their habitual sleep
162 patterns and light exposure.

163 The in-laboratory phase will take place in the climate chamber of the SenseLab, part of the Chair of
164 Building Technology and Climate Responsive Design at the Technical University of Munich (TUM),
165 based on a collaboration for the use of this facility. This phase will span nine consecutive evenings,
166 during which participants will arrive 6.5 hours before their habitual bedtime (HBT) and remain for 6
167 hours each night, before they leave 30 minutes prior to their HBT. Upon arrival, they will receive a
168 standardized meal (Huel) before spending 2.5 hours in dim light (10 lx). They will then be exposed to
169 either dim (10 lx) or bright (1000 lx) light conditions for two hours, followed by another 30 minutes in
170 dim light (10 lx) before leaving the laboratory. This protocol allows for controlled manipulation of
171 evening light exposure to assess its impact on physiological and cognitive responses.

172 Throughout each session, saliva samples will be collected every 30 minutes for melatonin analysis,
 173 sleepiness and visual comfort ratings will be recorded at the same intervals, and participants will
 174 complete a psychomotor vigilance test (PVT) every hour. iButtons will be used to assess skin
 175 temperature. The core body temperature will be monitored using an ingestible pill. These
 176 measurements will help determine how different light conditions influence circadian rhythms,
 177 alertness, and cognitive performance. The findings from this study will contribute to a better
 178 understanding of the role of evening light exposure in regulating human physiology and behaviour,
 179 with potential implications for optimizing light environments in real-world settings.

180 Objectives

181 The objectives of this pilotstudy are:

- 182 (1) To characterise inter-daily variability of melatonin production
- 183 (2) To characterise inter-daily variability of melatonin suppression by light
- 184 (3) To investigate carry-over effects of light-induced melatonin suppression

185 Study duration

186 Entire study

187 The entire pilotstudy will take place over a total of 4 months.

188 For each participant

189 Each participant in the pilotstudy will be enrolled for a total of 23 days, comprising an initial 7-day
 190 ambulatory monitoring period prior to the first laboratory evening, 9 days of laboratory evenings, and
 191 then a final 7-day period of ambulatory monitoring.

192 Study sample

193 Description of study sample

194 In this pilotstudy, we will recruit healthy participants aged 18-40 years with no systematic, ocular and
 195 retinal diseases, no psychiatric or neurological diseases, with normal sleep-wake behaviour, normal
 196 colour vision, and meet the following additional criteria:

197 Inclusion criteria

Domain	Criterion	Assessment method
Age	≥18, ≤40 years of age	Self-report
Biological sex	Men	Self-report
	Women with a natural menstrual cycle	
	Women taking monophasic combined oral contraceptives	
Physical health	Good physical health	Self-report
Mental health	Good mental health	Self-report
Ocular and retinal health	Good ocular and retinal health	Self-report

Short physical examination	Good health	Physicians
Normal colour vision	Normal colour vision	Ishihara plates
Basic English language skills	Ability to comprehend and communicate in basic English	Self-report

198 **Exclusion criteria**

Domain	Criterion	Assessment method
Biological sex	Women taking any other type of hormonal contraception	Self-report
BMI	<18 or >30	Calculation from measured height and weight
Medication use	Any use of medications	Self-report
Smoking	Habitual smoking	Self-report
Epilepsy	Diagnosis of epilepsy	Self-report
Substance abuse	Excessive alcohol use	AUDIT
Sleep	Poor sleep quality	PSQI >5
Chronotype	Extreme chronotype	MCTQ
Shift work	No shift work in the past 3 months	Self-report
Time zone travel	No inter-time zone travel in the past 3 months	Self-report
Pregnancy	Currently pregnant and < 12 months postpartum	Self-report
Endocrinal alteration	No hormonal imbalances	Self-report
Drug use	Any drug detected	AMP, BZD, COC, MOR/OPI, THC panel (nal von minden GmbH)
Alcohol	Any alcohol in breath	Breathalyzer

199 **Recruitment**

200 We will recruit participants through a variety of means. This will include a multi-modal strategy using
 201 posters, ads placed on the internet and in public, mailing list postings, the recruitment system SONA,
 202 word-of-mouth and invitation via the WhatsApp group of health and sports science students.
 203 Participants will be sent the participant information sheet with the informed consent form and will have
 204 the opportunity to participate in an information session demonstrating the lab and devices used in the
 205 pilotstudy prior to enrolling in the pilotstudy.

206 **Sample size**

207 In this pilotstudy, we will be following a strong within-subjects design, where each participant
 208 participates in a series of conditions, including serving as their own control. Acknowledging the
 209 exploratory character of this study, we expect to run it with a total sample size of 16 participants.

210 **Protocol**

211 **Overview**

212 The pilotstudy has four components: Screening, ambulatory monitoring before the in-laboratory
 213 session (7 days), a 9-day sequence of laboratory sessions during the evening, and final ambulatory
 214 monitoring (7 days) after the in-laboratory sessions. The screening aims to identify participants and

215 evaluate their suitability for the pilotstudy against a series of selection criteria. Once enrolled in the
 216 pilotstudy, participants will attend evening in-laboratory measurements and assessment on nine
 217 sequential days. The pilotstudy will take place in English.

218 **Location**

219 In the context of a collaboration with the Chair of Building Technology and Climate Responsive Design
 220 at the Technical University of Munich (TUM), all screening and in-laboratory visits will take place at
 221 the TUM SenseLab at the main campus

222 **Screening**

223 **Demographic variables**

224 At screening, we will ask participants for their age, sex and gender identity.

225 **Health variables**

226 Physical health will be assessed using a self-report. We will ask participants whether they are taking
 227 any medication, are smoking or have a diagnosis of epilepsy or having any hormonal imbalances.
 228 Additionally female participants will be asked about their menstrual health (MHQ), the specific type of
 229 monophasic combined oral contraceptive they are taking (if applicable) and fill out a reproductive
 230 status questionnaire. We will use an urine based pregnancy test at the beginning of the first in
 231 laboratory visit.

232 **Questionnaires**

233 During screening, participants will complete a series of questionnaires, delivered via the online
 234 platform REDCap on a server set up and maintained by the Chronobiology & Health team at TUM
 235 and will be acquainted via the app momentUM. The server is set up as a virtual machine hosted by
 236 the Leibniz-Rechenzentrum der Bayerischen Akademie der Wissenschaften.

237 *Health survey*

238 We will assess basic demographic and relevant health data from the participants.

239 *Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT)*

240 Participants will complete the Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT), an instrument to
 241 examine substance and alcohol abuse, in the self-report version.

242 *Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI)*

243 Participants will complete the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), an instrument to determine sleep
 244 quality.

245 *Munich Chronotype Questionnaire (MCTQ)*

246 Participants will complete the Munich Chronotype Questionnaire (MCTQ) to determine their
 247 chronotype.

248 *Light Exposure Behaviour Assessment (LEBA)*

249 Participants will complete the Light Exposure Behaviour Assessment (LEBA) instrument for
 250 determining habitual light exposure patterns.

251 **In-laboratory measurements**

252 Participants will come to laboratory 6,5 hours prior to their HBT and leave the laboratory 30 minutes
 253 before their HBT. Their HBT will be established using the information given at screening. From three
 254 days before the pilotstudy, participants will abstain from non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID)

255 and alcohol intake. On the day of the pilotstudy, participants will be asked to abstain from caffeine
 256 intake four hours after their habitual waketime and avoid acute physical activity. Four participants will
 257 be tested at a time.

258 **Anthropometric measurements**

259 At the beginning of the first visit, we will measure participant height and weight.

260 **Alcohol and THC test**

261 At the beginning of each laboratory evening, participants will be tested for alcohol and THC use.
 262 Participants will be asked to use a Breathalyzer (Alkoholtester ACE A) to determine blood alcohol
 263 content (BAC). Participants will also be asked to produce a urine sample in a collection device, which
 264 will then be tested using a multi-drug panel. Should either test be positive, participants will be removed
 265 from the pilotstudy.

266 **Saliva**

267 During the in-laboratory measurements, saliva will be sampled from participants every 30 minutes in
 268 order to analyse melatonin levels.

269 **Continuous glucose monitoring**

270 Participants will wear the Freestyle Libre Pro (Abbott Laboratories), a Continuous Glucose
 271 Monitoring (CGM) device, for continuous 24-hour glucose level monitoring.

272 **Skin temperature**

273 iButtons will be attached to the neck and ankle of participants during their visit of the laboratory to
 274 record skin temperature.

275 **Core body temperature**

276 Participants will ingest a pill, utilizing the Body Cap eCelsius system, to measure core body
 277 temperature. The device is CE certified, and data will be stored locally. To ensure participant safety,
 278 they will wear a wristband to prevent entry into an MRI environment until the pill has been naturally
 279 expelled. The pill is expected to be expelled within 24-48 hours following ingestion.

280 **Light stimuli**

281 **Stimulus presentation**

282 We will study two distinct light exposure conditions over a five-hour period in each lab session,
 283 presented on different study days. Each session will begin with 2.5 hours in dim light (10 lx),
 284 followed by 2 hours of exposure to either dim light (10 lx) or bright light (1000 lx). The session will
 285 conclude with 30 minutes in dim light (10 lx) before departure. Stimuli will be delivered using room
 286 illumination or specialized light sources.

287 **Core body temperature**

288 We will continuously measure participants' core body temperature using the BodyCap e-Celsius
 289 system, starting shortly after they finish their standardized dinner in the laboratory. This system
 290 involves the use of an ingestible temperature pill, which connects to an external device via RFID and
 291 measures corebody temperature. The device is CE-certified and data will be stored locally.
 292 Participants will eject the pill with 24-48 hours of ingestion. As the device is not MRI safe, participants
 293 will receive a wristband indicating that they cannot enter an MRI scanner. The participants will be
 294 asked to wear a certain type of clothing to ensure the same clothing factor of 0.5, which means they
 295 should wear normal underwear, long sleeves with light material, long trousers or skirts made of

296 normal/light material (excluding jeans). They should also wear regular short socks (not stockings or
297 tights) and regular dress or sports shoes (no heavy boots).

298 **Visual comfort**

299 Every 30 minutes, participants will complete a brief visual comfort questionnaire delivered on digital
300 tablets or via pen and paper.

301 **Karolinska Sleepiness Scale (KSS)**

302 This scale measures the subjective level of sleepiness at a particular moment in time via self-
303 reporting. It will be delivered via digital tablets or pen and paper.

304 **Psychomotor vigilance test (PVT) attention test**

305 Every 60 minutes, participants will perform an auditory psychomotor vigilance test (PVT) using the
306 PVT-192 Psychomotor Vigilance Task Monitor (Ambulatory Monitoring, Inc.). This test measures
307 sustained attention and reaction time. It can be ideal for assessing alertness changes due to sleep
308 deprivation or light exposure.

309 **Salivary melatonin**

310 Every 30 minutes, participants will give saliva samples throughout the protocol. Upon collection, these
311 samples will be centrifuged and frozen.

312 **Participant monitoring during in-laboratory sessions**

313 During the study period, participants are kindly requested to minimize their movements and, if
314 possible, maintain the same sitting position for the majority of the time.

315 **Timeline**

316 For each in-laboratory visit, participants will arrive in the laboratory 6.5 hours before their HBT. They
317 will firstly be reminded of the instructions and the requirements to participate in the session especially
318 about sustained participations and signing an informed consent.

319 During the first hour of the visit, they will complete a breathalyser, to ensure they are not under the
320 influence of alcohol or THC. Then, they will be provided with a standardised meal (Huel, which has a
321 well-balanced macronutrient profile and portion sizes will be adjusted based on participants metabolic
322 requirements following the Mifflin-St. Jeor formula) and then ingest the pill which is part BodyCap e-
323 Celsius system to initialise the core body temperature measures. In addition, iButtons will be attached
324 to their neck and ankle.

325 The experiment will begin 5.5 hours before their habitual bedtime. Participants will sit on a couch or
326 chair while they provide an initial saliva sample and then will complete a battery of behavioural tests
327 that includes a sleepiness questionnaire (KSS), a visual comfort questionnaire, and a Psychomotor
328 Vigilance Test (PVT). After this, the lights in the room will be set to a dim state (10 lux). This light
329 stimulus will be maintained for the 2.5 hours of the experiment, before a 2-hour period of different
330 exposures (10 lux or 1000 lux). Every 30 minutes, participants will again provide a saliva sample and
331 complete the behavioural test of sleepiness and alertness (every 30 min) and attention test (every 60
332 min.)

333 They will be offered breaks every 30 minutes after the tests and will be allowed toilet breaks whenever
334 needed, where they will wear blue light blocking glasses. Throughout this part of the experiment,
335 except when completing the battery of tests, participants will be allowed to read printed materials
336 and/or listen to pre-selected audiobooks or musical albums.

337 The participants will depart from the lab 30 minutes before their HBT. The next day, the participants
 338 will come back 6.5 hours before there HBT, and the same process will be completed on each evening.

339 The light exposure sequence will be selected to correspond to a 2-label, 3-level counterbalanced De
 340 Bruijn sequence. In this sequence, all transition 2-back triplets occur once, i.e. [Dim, Dim, Dim]; [Dim,
 341 Dim, Bright]; [Dim; Bright; Bright] and so on. There are two possible 2-label, 3-level DeBruijn
 342 sequences:

Day	Sequence A	Sequence B
Day 1	Dim (10 lx)	Dim (10 lx)
Day 2	Dim (10 lx)	Bright (1000 lx)
Day 3	Dim (10 lx)	Bright (1000 lx)
Day 4	Bright (1000 lx)	Bright (1000 lx)
Day 5	Bright (1000 lx)	Dim (10 lx)
Day 6	Bright (1000 lx)	Dim (10 lx)
Day 7	Dim (10 lx)	Dim (10 lx)
Day 8	Bright (1000 lx)	Bright (1000 lx)
Day 9	Dim (10 lx)	Dim (10 lx)

343 Participants will be tested in groups of 4 participants. Each group will be randomly assigned one
 344 sequence.

345 Sampling of biological materials

346 Saliva

347 Saliva will be sampled every 30 minutes using Salivette collection devices. These devices are
 348 standard for saliva collection and later assay. In brief, participants chew on a cotton swab for 5 minutes
 349 and place it into a plastic collection tube. The salivette will then be stored for later processing.

350 The saliva will be assayed for melatonin using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The
 351 assaying will be performed by the bioanalytics company NovoLyTiX. The samples will be destroyed
 352 after completion of the study. All samples will be retained securely until the study has been completed
 353 and all data have been published.

354 Instruments

355 In this pilotstudy, we will use various instruments for visual stimulation and measurements. The
 356 following table gives the devices, the manufacturer, their purpose, and any certification status.

Device	Manufacturer	Purpose	Certification
ActLumus	Condor (São Paulo, Brasil)	Measurement of rest-activity cycles and light exposure	IEC60601-1:2006, IEC60601-1-2:2007, IEC60601-1-11:2010

PVT-192 Psychomotor Vigilance	CWE, Inc.	Reaction Time	Class I, Self -Certified
GT3X	ActiGraph, LLC	Measurement of rest-activity cycles	–
Freestyle Libre Pro	Abbott	Continuous Glucose Monitoring	FDA
e-Celsius	BodyCap	Measurement of core body temperature using an ingestible pill	CE
Skin temperature, iButton	Analog Devices	Recording skin temperature using iButtons attached to the neck and ankle.	DS1922L-F5

357 Appropriate certificates are appended in Appendix A. All devices were purchased from internal funds
 358 of the investigator and were not sponsored by the manufacturer(s).

359 Statistical analysis plan

360 Overview

361 The statistical analysis will assess the effects of light exposure on circadian and metabolic physiology,
 362 focusing on melatonin suppression, psychomotor vigilance, core body temperature, skin temperature,
 363 , glucose metabolism, and subjective sleepiness. Analyses will follow a within-subjects design,
 364 leveraging the counterbalanced De Bruijn sequence to minimize order effects.

365 Main Hypotheses

366 In line with the objectives of this study, three main hypotheses can be proposed.

Hypothesis	Outcome measure	Statistical test
H1: Light exposure (1000 lx) leads to greater melatonin suppression compared to dim light (10 lx)	Salivary melatonin concentration (pg/mL)	Linear mixed-effects model (LMM) with condition (dim vs. bright) and time as fixed effects, participant as a random effect
H2: The impact of light exposure on melatonin suppression is modulated by prior light history	Preceding day's light exposure (lux-hour, logged from wearable light logger)	LMM with preceding light exposure as a covariate
H3: Individual variability in melatonin suppression is significant	Individual differences in suppression slope (Δ melatonin per lx exposure)	Variance component analysis in LMM; hierarchical clustering to stratify sensitivity subgroups.

367 Secondary Hypotheses

368 Additionally, the following secondary hypotheses will be tested.

369

Hypothesis	Outcome measure	Statistical test
H4: Bright light exposure reduces subjective sleepiness compared to dim light	Karolinska Sleepiness Scale (KSS) scores	Repeated-measures ANOVA with light condition and time as factors
H5: Bright light exposure enhances psychomotor vigilance	Psychomotor Vigilance Test (PVT) reaction time (ms), PVT lapses (RT > 500 ms)	Paired t-tests / LMM with time and condition as fixed effects
H6: Core body temperature follows a different trajectory under bright vs. dim light	Body temperature (°C) measured via ingestible sensor	Generalized Additive Model (GAM) to model non-linear trends
H7: Distal-proximal skin temperature gradient follows a different trajectory under bright vs. dim light	Difference between distal and proximal temperature (°C) measured on the skin	Generalized Additive Model (GAM) to model non-linear trends
H8: Bright light exposure influences glucose metabolism	CGM-derived glucose levels (mg/dL), Glucose variability metrics (e.g., standard deviation, MAGE)	LMM with light condition as a fixed effect, participant as a random effect

370 Sample size justification

371 Based on prior studies (Phillips et al., 2019; Higuchi et al., 2013), we expect an effect size of $d = 0.8$
 372 for melatonin suppression. Due to the exploratory character of this study and due to resource
 373 limitations, we will aim of 16 participants. Due to the strong within-subjects design, we expect that the
 374 results of this pilotstudy will be informative.

375 Participant remuneration

376 Participants will be remunerated for their time, with a rate of €10 for each evening session. If they
 377 complete all sessions, they will receive a bonus of up to €450, leading to a total maximum
 378 compensation of €540. If participants drop out of the study, no bonus will be paid.

379 Risks and benefits

380 Participants may find adhering to a regular sleep-wake cycle for the nine-day study period challenging.
 381 To minimize this risk, our screening process identifies individuals who are likely to maintain a stable
 382 sleep schedule without difficulty.

383 Spending nine consecutive evenings in the laboratory may cause discomfort or fatigue. However, our
 384 research team will closely monitor participants throughout all lab visits and provide necessary support
 385 if they report any distress.

386 Wearing multiple devices, including an actigraph tracker, light logger, and continuous glucose
 387 monitoring (CGM) devices, for an extended period may be inconvenient or uncomfortable. The CGM
 388 device requires a small sensor to be inserted under the skin, which may cause mild discomfort or
 389 irritation. Participants will receive detailed instructions on proper sensor placement, care, and
 390 troubleshooting, and the research team will be available to assist with any issues.

391 The CGM device may also cause mild skin irritation, infection risk at the insertion site, or sensor
 392 adhesion issues. To minimize these risks, participants will be provided with proper cleaning
 393 instructions, and sensor replacement will be available if necessary.

394 Participants may also experience mild discomfort from repeated saliva sampling throughout the
395 pilotstudy. However, saliva collection is a non-invasive method for assessing melatonin levels, making
396 it a safer and less burdensome alternative to blood sampling.

397 Some participants may find frequent saliva collection inconvenient or experience dry mouth. To
398 mitigate this, participants will be informed whether water intake is allowed before sampling to reduce
399 discomfort.

400 Repeated evening visits and sleep schedule restrictions may lead to mental and physical fatigue. To
401 address this, participants will be offered rest breaks as needed, and fatigue levels will be monitored
402 throughout the pilotstudy. The research team will intervene if excessive fatigue is reported.

403 Despite these risks, the pilotstudy offers significant benefits by advancing our understanding of how
404 evening light exposure influences circadian physiology, neuroendocrine function, and metabolic
405 regulation. This research has potential implications for sleep health, workplace lighting
406 recommendations, and clinical applications for individuals with circadian rhythm disorders or
407 metabolic conditions. Participants may also gain insight into their own sleep patterns and physiological
408 responses to light, which could help inform healthier lifestyle habits.

409 Overall, we have carefully evaluated the potential risks and benefits to ensure participant safety while
410 maximizing the scientific value of the study.

411 **Data protection**

412 **Legal consent**

413 Prior to any data collection, participants will be informed of how their data are processed and will have
414 ample opportunities to ask questions. Participants will receive paper consent forms and detailed
415 information about processing of their personal data, which will include their name and signature.
416 These consent forms (see attached *Legal Declaration of Consent* including *Information Sheet* in
417 accordance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation) will be retained in a locked cabinet at
418 TUM. Only selected people will have keys to this cabinet. Upon the start of their participation, in-lab
419 subjects are assigned a random subject ID number. This subject number will be used to label data
420 obtained on the task. At no point will the subjects' names be tied to their subject number. There will
421 be no method to go from subject ID number to subject name or match subject responses on the task
422 to subject identity.

423 **Pseudonymization**

424 At enrolment of the pilotstudy, participants will be assigned a pseudonym participant ID which is
425 necessary to ensure scheduling of appointments and planning of logistics of participation, will be
426 stored in password-protected and encrypted spreadsheet in a restricted TUM location. The linkage
427 list between name and participant ID, the password will only be known to the experimenter and PI and
428 cannot be read, copied, modified or removed by unauthorized persons.

429 All data collected in this project will be labelled using the pseudonyms and stored directly in a
430 pseudonymised form. I.e. the data will be collected under a numerical ID without a reference to contact
431 details and processed without any assignment to personal data of the participants.

432 The documentation of data and its archiving occurs in a pseudonymised form in a protected electronic
433 database, to which only a limited number of authorised employees have access, including here

434 doctoral students, who are obligated to professional and data secrecy. This data secrecy obligation
435 will also continue to exist after termination of their employment.

436 **Processing of personal data during the study**

437 The processing of personal data will be carried out in such a way that the data can no longer be
438 attributed to a data subject without the use of additional information. The additional information is kept
439 separately and is subject to appropriate technical and organizational measures. Once data have been
440 collected either in-laboratory or online, they are stored on secure, password-protected lab computers
441 and server space accessible only to trained laboratory personnel.

442 Collected data may be used for the preparation of anonymised scientific research work and may also
443 be published and used in an anonymised form in medical journals and scientific publications, so that
444 a direct reference to participant person cannot be established.

445 **Data analysis**

446 The collected and saved data will be classified as health data under the "very high" protection level.
447 The transfer of the analysis from the laboratory will be done pseudonymized using participant ID, so
448 the laboratory cannot make a connection between the person and samples. Furthermore, the sample
449 analysis results will be delivered in encrypted form to the study leader at TUM. All participating
450 laboratory physicians and employees are subject to medical confidentiality as stipulated by German
451 law.

452 **List of data types**

Type of data	Location	Note
Participant name	Informed consent forms	Forms will be locked in a storage cabinet
Participant signature		
Name and participant ID linkage list	Password-protected and encrypted spreadsheet on shared network drive accessible only to project personnel	Only the project team have access
Sleep diaries collected in sleep-wake stabilisation period	Data collected on password-protected storage server	All digital data will be pseudonymised and labelled with participant ID
Demographic data, including age, sex, gender identity and Questionnaire results	Data collected on password-protected storage server	
Saliva samples	Freezers at TUM, shipped to bioanalytics facilities	Saliva samples will be pseudonymised and labelled with participant ID
Melatonin concentrations obtained from saliva samples	Spreadsheets and data files on shared network drive accessible only to project personnel	All digital data will be pseudonymised and labelled with participant ID
Data from wrist-worn activity tracker		
Data from wearable light logger		
Performance data from PVT		
Data from iButtons		

453 **Participant information sheet and informed consent form**

454 The participant information sheet and informed consent form is attached to the application.

455 **Study materials**

456 All study materials are attached to the ethics application (Appendix B).

457

458 **Appendix A**

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460 2023.05.04_AppendixA_ABPMpro.pdf

461 2023.05.04_AppendixA_ActiGraphGT3X.pdf

462 2023.05.04_AppendixA_ActTrust.pdf

463 2023.05.04_AppendixA_BodyCap.pdf

464 2023.05.04_AppendixA_Fibion.pdf

465 2023.05.02_AppendixA_Freestyle_Libre_Pro.pdf

466 2023.05.04_AppendixA_i-Button.pdf

467 2023.05.04_AppendixA_OMRON.pdf

468 2023.05.04_AppendixA_Tobii3pro.pdf

469 2023.05.04_AppendixA_U-Rhythm.pdf

470 2023.05.04_AppendixA_SOP_Cleaning_U-RHYTH_.pdf

471 2023.05.04_AppendixA_SOP_Reporting_sampling_outcome.pdf

472 2023.05.04_AppendixA_SOP_sample_retrieval.pdf

473 2023.05.04_AppendixA_SOP_Starting_to_sample_with_U-RHYTHM.pdf

474 2023.05.04_AppendixA_SOP_U-RHYTHM_Checklist_and_log_generic.pdf

475 2023.05.04_AppendixA_SOP_Ending_U-RHYTHM_sampling_session.pdf

476

477 **Appendix B**

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479 2023.05.04_AppendixB_ASHRAE-en.pdf

480 2023.05.04_AppendixB_AUDIT-en.pdf

481 2023.05.04_AppendixB_Demographics-en.pdf

482 2023.05.04_AppendixB_Device_Tolerability-en.pdf

483 2023.05.04_AppendixB_MCTQ-en.pdf

484 2023.05.04_AppendixB_MHQ-en.pdf

485 2023.05.04_AppendixB_MoodandVisualcomfort-en.pdf

486 2023.05.04_AppendixB_KSS-en.pdf

487 2023.05.04_AppendixB_LEBA-en.pdf

488 2023.05.04_AppendixB_PSQI-en.pdf

489 2023.05.04_AppendixB_ReproductiveQ-en.pdf

490 2023.05.04_AppendixB_SleepDiary-en.pdf

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